

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 83

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 83

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 83:0 A Song, a Psalm of Asaph.</p>	<p>Psa. 83:1 שִׁיר מִזְמוֹר לְאַסָּף : 2</p>
<p>Psa. 83:1 O God, “do not remain quiet;</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים אֵל-דָּמִי-לֵךְ אֶל-תַּחֲרֹשׁ וְאֶל-תִּשְׁקֹט אֵל : 3 כִּי-הִנֵּה אוֹיְבֶיךָ</p>
<p>^bDo not be silent and, O God, do not be still.</p>	<p>יַהֲמִיזוּן וְיִמְשְׁנֹאִיד נָשְׂאוּ רֹאשׁ : 4</p>
<p>² For behold, Your enemies “make an uproar,</p>	<p>עַל-עַמֶּךָ יַעֲרִימוּ סוּד וְיִתְעַצּוּ עַל-צְפוֹנֵיךָ : 5</p>
<p>And ^bthose who hate You have ^{1c}exalted themselves.</p>	<p>אָמְרוּ לָכֹו וְנִכְחַתֵּם מִגּוֹי וְלֹא-יִזְכָּר שֵׁם-יִשְׂרָאֵל עוֹד : 6</p>
<p>³ They “make shrewd plans against Your people,</p>	<p>כִּי נֹעְצוּ לֵב יַחֲדוּ עָלֶיךָ בְּרִית יִכְרְתוּ : 7</p>
<p>And ¹conspire together against ^bYour ²treasured ones.</p>	<p>אֶהְלִי אֲדוֹם וְיִשְׁמַעֲאֵלִים מוֹאָב וְהַגְרִים : 8</p>
<p>⁴ They have said, “Come, and ^alet us wipe them out ¹as a nation,</p>	<p>וְעַמְלֵק פְּלִשְׁת עַם-יִשְׁבִּי צוּר : 9</p>
<p>That the ^bname of Israel be remembered no more.”</p>	<p>גַּם-אֲשׁוּר נְלוּהָ עִמָּם הִיוּ זְרוּעַ לְבַנְי-לוֹט סֶלָה : 10</p>
<p>⁵ For they have ^{1a}conspired together with one mind;</p>	<p>עֲשֵׂה-לָהֶם כְּמַדִּין פְּסִיסְרָא כִּיבִין בְּנַחַל קִישׁוֹן : 11</p>
<p>Against You they make a covenant:</p>	<p>נִשְׁמְדוּ בְּעֵין-דָּאָר הִיוּ אֲמֵן לְאֲדָמָה : 12</p>
<p>⁶ The tents of “Edom and the ^bIshmaelites,</p>	<p>שִׁיתְמוּ גְדִיבְמוּ כְּעַרְב וְכּוֹזָאָב וְכַזְּבָח וְכַצְּלָמָנֹעַ כָּל-נְסִיכְמוּ : 13</p>
<p>^aMoab and the ^aHagrites;</p>	<p>אֲשֶׁר אָמְרוּ נִירְשָׁה לָנוּ אֵת נְאוֹת אֱלֹהִים : 14</p>
<p>⁷ “Gebal and ^bAmmon and ^cAmalek, ^aPhilistia with the inhabitants of ^aTyre;</p>	<p>שִׁיתְמוּ כַּגִּלְגָּל כְּקֶשׁ לְפַנִּי-רוּחַ : 15</p>
<p>⁸ “Assyria also has joined with them; They have become ¹a help to the ^bchildren of Lot. ²Selah.</p>	<p>כָּאֵשׁ תִּבְעַר-יַעַר וְכִלְהָבָה תִּלְהַט הַרִים : 16</p>
<p>Deal with them “as with Midian,</p>	<p>בֵּן תַּרְדֵּפֶם בְּסַעֲרֶךָ וּבְסוּפְתֶךָ תִּבְהַלֵּם : 17</p>
<p>Psa. 83:9 Deal with them “as with Midian,</p>	<p>קָלוּז וְיִבְקֹשׁוּ שְׁמֶיךָ יְהוָה : 18</p>

As ^bwith Sisera *and* Jabin at the
torrent of Kishon,

¹⁰ Who were destroyed at En-dor,
Who ^abecame as dung for the
ground.

¹¹ Make their nobles like ^aOreb and
Zeeb

And all their princes like ^bZebah
and Zalmunna,

¹² Who said, “^aLet us possess for
ourselves

The ^bpastures of God.”

Psa. 83:13 O my God, make them like
the ^{1a}whirling dust,

Like ^bchaff before the wind.

¹⁴ Like ^afire that burns the forest

And like a flame that ^bsets the
mountains on fire,

¹⁵ So pursue them ^awith Your
tempest

And terrify them with Your storm.

¹⁶ ^aFill their faces with dishonor,

That they may seek Your name, O

LORD.

¹⁷ Let them be ^aashamed and
dismayed forever,

And let them be humiliated and
perish,

¹⁸ That they may ^aknow that ^bYou
alone, whose name is the LORD,

Are the ^cMost High over all the
earth.

וַיִּבְהֲלוּ עַד-עֵר וַיִּחַפְּרוּ וַיֵּאָבְדוּ :
¹⁹ וַיִּדְעוּ כִּי-אַתָּה שֶׁמֶן יְהוָה לְבַבְךָ
עֲלִיּוֹן עַל-כָּל-הָאָרֶץ :

References

Psalm 83:1

^aPs 28:1; 35:22

^bPs 109:1

Psalm 83:2

¹Lit *lifted up the head*

^aPs 2:1; Is 17:12

^bPs 81:15

^cJudg 8:28; Zech 1:21

Psalm 83:3

¹Or *consult*

²Or *hidden ones*

^aPs 64:2; Is 29:15

^bPs 27:5; 31:20

Psalm 83:4

¹Lit *from*

^aEsth 3:6; Ps 74:8; Jer 48:2

^bPs 41:5; Jer 11:19

Psalm 83:5

¹Or *consulted*

^aPs 2:2; Dan 6:7

Psalm 83:6

^{a2}Chr 20:10; Ps 137:7

^bGen 25:12-16

^{c2}Chr 20:10

^{d1}Chr 5:10

Psalm 83:7

^aJosh 13:5; Ezek 27:9

^{b2}Chr 20:10

^{c1}Sam 15:2

^{d1}Sam 4:1; 29:1

^eEzek 27:3; Amos 1:9

Psalm 83:8

¹Lit *an arm*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^a2 Kin 15:19

^bDeut 2:9

Psalm 83:9

^aJudg 7:1-24

^bJudg 4:7, 15, 21-24

Psalm 83:10

^aZeph 1:17

Psalm 83:11

^aJudg 7:25

^bJudg 8:12, 21

Psalm 83:12

^a2 Chr 20:11

^bPs 132:13

Psalm 83:13

¹Or *tumbleweed*

^aIs 17:13

^bJob 21:18; Ps 35:5; Is 40:24; Jer 13:24

Psalm 83:14

^aIs 9:18

^bEx 19:18; Deut 32:22

Psalm 83:15

^aJob 9:17; Ps 58:9

Psalm 83:16

^aJob 10:15; Ps 109:29; 132:18

Psalm 83:17

^aPs 35:4; 70:2

Psalm 83:18

^aPs 59:13

^hPs 86:10; Is 45:21
Ps 9:2; 18:13; 97:9

Targum

Psa. 83:1 A song and Psalm composed by Asaph. ² God, do not become silent; do not be uncaring, and do not be quiet, O God. ³ For, behold, your enemies are stirred up, and your foes have lifted their head. ⁴ Against your people they have contrived a secret plan, and they take counsel together against things hidden in your treasuries. ⁵ They say, “Come, let us conceal them from being a people, and the name of Israel will not be mentioned again.” ⁶ For they take counsel together against you with all their heart, and make a covenant on your account. ⁷ The tents of the Edomites and Arabs, the Moabites and Hungarites. ⁸ The Gublites and Ammonites and Amalekites, the Philistines with the inhabitants of Tyre. ⁹ Also Sennacherib, king of Assyria, allied himself with them; they became a support for the sons of Lot forever. ¹⁰ Do to them as you did to Midian, to Sisera, and as you did to Jabin at the stream of Kishon. ¹¹ They were destroyed at the spring of Dor; they were as dung that is trampled on the earth. ¹² Make them and their chiefs like Oreb and like Zeeb; and all their kings like Zeba and Zalmunna. ¹³ Who had said, “We will inherit for ourselves all the fields of the god Elohim.” ¹⁴ O my God, make them like a wheel that keeps on rolling and does not stop, down a slope; and like straw before a storm. ¹⁵ Like fire that burns in the forest, and like the flame that ignites the plants of the mountains. ¹⁶ Thus will you pursue them with your storm wind, and you will frighten them with your gale. ¹⁷ Fill their faces with shame, and they will seek your name, O LORD. ¹⁸ They will be ashamed and terrified for ages upon ages; and they will be disgraced and will perish. ¹⁹ And they will know that you, your name the LORD, are alone supreme over all the inhabitants of the earth.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

This Psalm is based on the accomplishments of King Jehoshafat, which can be found in 2 Chronicles. This king renovated the justice system in Judea. Judea was attacked during his reign by the Ammonites, Moabites, Aramites, and Seirites (Edom). The Psalmist reveals the deeper intention of these attacks. These nations not only wanted to destroy Judah, but they also wanted to remove the LORD's name from the earth. Jehoshaphat used the power of song as his chief weapon against his foes. He declared that the LORD does reign over the universe. Judah's survival was the proof.

General notes on Spiritual Awareness in this Psalm

This part of history repeats a theme that is still in use today. With the LORD, anything is possible. Jehoshaphat was outnumbered by the surrounding nations that wanted to destroy Judah. Had that occurred, the name of the LORD and His presence would have been lost upon the earth forever? Perhaps that is too powerful a statement. It is unknown if the LORD would have tried to find another Chosen People. However, the LORD had a covenant with Abraham that his descendants would always be maintained. At least a remnant of the people would always survive. Therefore, as long as Judah lived by the Ten Commandments and the Torah, the LORD would be with them. During Jehoshaphat's reign, he brought the nation back from idolatry to following the ways of the LORD. Therefore, when the attacks came, the LORD was with Judah, and the LORD proved to the world that there was one supreme God. Monotheism was only a part of Hebraic culture at that time. Therefore, the nations who attacked Judah believed their god was inferior to the God of Israel.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

